

Architecture Creative Industry: Designing Space for the New Normal Era of Pandemic COVID19

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Abstract:- Architecture is one of Creative Industry Sectors based on the Indonesian Standard Classification of Business Fields (KBLI). Architecture is a creative act related to building design services, including these are construction details, landscape architecture and interior architecture. Nowadays, in this Covid 19 Pandemic, the Creative Industry of Architecture speaks strongly. Discussion made on How the Architectural Society responds to the implementation of the Creative Industry during Pandemic toward the Nation's Socio-Economic recovery? The qualitative research methodology was used, such as literature studies, theoretical and comparative analysis in order to finding out architectural creativity responding to the Pandemic Designs' solutions. World's architectural discussion today, are: How did the architecture change due to the changes in lifestyle during the Pandemic - called the New Normal Era or Adaptation to New Life-behaved. The results indicate that the field of architecture plays an important role for the continuation of the new normal life, other than the fields of economy, education and health. The concept of spatial in architecture are required to change and adjust based on the narrative and standards of new normal life. The Health Protocols applied has made the Architecture shifts in many ways. The findings show the novelty that pragmatic changes of spatial identity, functions, design, including this interior design and the use of architectural technology which those all the impacts of the Pandemic's New-Normal Era.

Keywords:- *New-Normal Era, Pandemic Covid19 design, Architectural Pandemic, Creative design Pandemic, Adaptation behavior.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The year 2020 was the beginning of the case for the spread of Covid-19 in Indonesia and became an international epidemic disaster (Burhan, et al., 2020). The Covid-19 outbreak has become a case that disrupts human health and has a wide impact (Ministry of Health of Indonesia, 2020). This is faced by all countries, both developing and developed countries. Indonesia has also been impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic, even affecting developments and conditions in all fields. Not only health problems, the spread of Covid-19 has an impact and affects various sectors (Sugihamretha, 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic has changed many things in life and in various fields including work. One that is quite prominent is behavior change. The term "new normal" then became very popular. The New Normal includes (1) wearing a mask when leaving the house or interacting with

other people whose health status is unknown; (2) washing hands using soap with running water or using an alcohol-based antiseptic liquid/hand sanitizer; (3) maintain a minimum distance of one meter from other people and avoid crowds, crowds, and crowds; and (4) increase body resistance by implementing clean and healthy living behavior. In the context of "maintaining a minimum distance of one meter from other people and avoiding crowds, crowds, and crowds".

The concept of "New Normal" has a significant impact on changes in the activities of the community and the existing spatial arrangement, both in the interior and exterior realms. The adjustments made by the architect to respond to the Covid-19 pandemic changed the existing order. Architectural Design Solutions as a result of the Covid-19 Pandemic situation occurred for changes in the function of public spaces, workspaces, homes, interior design and the use of architectural support technology. This study looks at the extent of the impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the spatial arrangement as a result of the implementation of the Health Protocol from the new normal life.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Indonesia is a maritime country that is rich in natural resources. From Sabang to Merauke, from spices and other food sources to livestock, they are the main production factors in the country. There are also more and more industries that take advantage of these factors to develop them into something useful for the field of employment and for social life. However, as the times progressed, the concept of the economy underwent changes and a new concept called the creative economy was born.

The creative industry itself is basically an industry that originates from the utilization of someone's creativity, skills, and talents that have the potential to create prosperity and employment by focusing on generating and exploiting the creative power and creativity and intellectual property of the individual.

The creative industry currently has a very important role in the economy of a country, not only in developing countries like Indonesia. In Indonesia, the creative industry is developing rapidly, experts and economists state that part of the country's income is contributed by the creative industry which continues to grow and develop all the time. This cannot be separated because the creative industry has a role in improving the economy of a country globally. The creative industry is closely related to the level of human creativity as the main source of driving the wheels of the economy. The number of creative industrial sectors created

is the fruit of creativity and innovation developed by someone.

John Howkins defines creative economy as the creation of value as a result of idea. In an interview with Donna Ghelfi of the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), Howkins describes the creative economy as an economic activity in society that spends most of its time generating ideas, not just doing routine and repetitive things. Howkins also revealed about the creative industry, namely, industries that have superior characteristics on the side of creativity in producing various creative designs that are attached to the goods or services produced.

In Indonesia, the creative industry is developing rapidly, experts and economists state that part of the country's income is contributed by the creative industry which continues to grow and develop all the time. The creative industry itself according to the Indonesian Ministry of Trade is an industry that originates from the use of individual activities, skills and talents to create prosperity and employment opportunities by producing and exploiting the creative power and creativity of the individual. In addition to agriculture, the creative industry is one sector that contributes quite high to the national economy. It is different from other sectors which are highly dependent on natural resources. In the creative industry, human resources are the main force. This is because the products produced from this sector come from creative ideas created by human thought. The Indonesian Creative Economy Agency (Berkaf) has established 16 sub-sectors that are supported in the creative industry, including game application and development, architecture, interior design, visual communication design, product design, fashion, film, photography, crafts, culinary, music, publishing, advertising, performing arts, fine arts, as well as television and radio.

Indonesia's creative economy statistics state that the Creative Economy Sector contributes to the national economy is dominated by three sub-sectors, namely culinary with 41.69%, fashion 18.15%, and crafts 15.70% (Berkaf and BPS, 2016). The three highest creative economy sub-sectors that are starting to show their contribution to GDP (Gross Domestic Product) can be collaborated with the tourism sector, so that the Indonesian economy can no longer be more independent and can reduce dependence on other countries. However, at this time the pandemic conditions have such an impact on the creative economy sector and we will all contribute in thinking and discussing about it.

Architecture includes 14 Creative Industry Sectors in accordance with the Indonesian Standard Classification of Business Fields (KBLI), that are included as: Advertising; Architecture; Art Market; Craft; Design; fashion; Video, Film & Photography; Interactive Games; Music; Performing Arts; Publishing & Printing; Computer Services & Software; Television & Radio; Research & Development.

Architectural is the one creative industry sub-sector. Architecture itself is a creative activity related to building design services, construction cost planning, conservation of heritage buildings, overall construction supervision from the macro level (Town planning, urban design, landscape architecture) to the micro level (construction details, for example: garden architecture, design interior). For example, this industry is engaged in projects such as historical heritage buildings, construction supervision, urban planning, consulting on engineering and engineering activities such as civil buildings and mechanical and electrical engineering. The of Indonesia's creative sub-sectors highlighted like Architecture contributed to National economy for 2.3% and Interior Design for 0.16% (Berkaf and BPS, 2016).

Some Examples of Creative Architectural Industry Concepts in general are Local Wisdom like Feng Shui, Psychology Architecture and Islamic Architecture. etc. However, during the Covid 19 Pandemic today, Architects are talking more on the Architecture Creative Industry, particularly how the architectural society responds to the implementation of the creative industry during Pandemic toward the nation's Socio-Economic recovery?

In the context of a broaden example related to Creative Industry in Architecture, the creative industry has advantages in terms of creativity, especially in producing creative designs that represent a product or service. The architectural creative industry is one type of creative industry that is related to the design of a building, building construction planning, construction supervision, and conservation of heritage buildings. In the creative industry, the architectural creative industry has 2 roles, namely the macro level and the micro level. Meanwhile, at the macro level, it is the overall construction of the building. Examples such as planning for making town planning, urban design, landscape architecture, and so on. While the micro level is to carry out construction or renovation of buildings, but on a small scale. Examples such as making garden architectural details, interior design, and may others.

How Important and Interesting Concepts in the Architectural Creative Industry is interesting to explore and discuss. Every architectural product must have a concept (For companies often use Vision: For example, 'giving a step to a bright vision or future' which means providing a step for a better vision or future. Besides that, the Creative Architectural Industry aside from pouring their abilities and knowledge, it would be nice if it was poured into something that could generate profits and be useful as an opportunity for others in terms of employment and at the same time minimize the number of unemployment rates in Indonesia, especially in Jakarta. The architecture and interior design sub-sectors can also have an impact on the creative economy, especially in Jakarta. This strong evidence provides a statement that the architectural and interior design industries in the creative economy have many benefits, not only in the field of employment, but also for the environment and social life.

III. METHODOLOGY

The qualitative research methodology was used, such as literature studies, theoretical and comparative analysis in order to finding out architectural creativity responding to the Pandemic Designs’ solutions. World’s architectural issues discussed, is: How did the architecture change due to the changes in lifestyle during the Pandemic - called the New Normal Era or Adaptation to New Life-behaved.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Discussion is formulated by two architectural concepts. It consists of Spatial Concept and Technological Concept. In addition to that, Urban Contemporer Issues & Users’ Hygiene is explored.

A. Spatial Concepts

a) Spatial Concept: Public Space

Transmission of the Covid-19 virus between humans who carry out communal activities or in mass crowds requires conceptual changes to public spaces, whether they are open spaces such as squares, city walks, plazas, city parks, car free days, and public spaces such as markets, malls, schools etc. This is as stated by Dr. Hans Henri P. Kluge who is WHO Regional Director for the European region as quoted by Tempo.co, said that the facilities must apply strictly the regulation in the implementation of the new normal life (The Decree of the Minister of Health Number HK.01.07/MENKES/328/2020 concerning Guidelines for the Prevention and Control of Covid-19 in Office and Industrial Workplaces in Supporting Business Continuity in a Pandemic Situation). In addition to Public space, The housing occupied by the elderly and dense settlement.

b) Public Space: Traditional Market

Public space is closely related to the behavior of crowding, chatting, touching, face-to-face, which almost eliminates the distance between users. We know markets where market visitors jostle each other in buying and selling transactions so that they can just pass through the market streets. Most behavior is tolerated by users because the market which is a public space is understood as a shared space that can be accessed and used by anyone, therefore we almost never find conflicts between market visitors due to touching each other.

Fig. 1: Market is a place where visitors jostle each other in buying and selling transactions so that they can just pass through the market streets and their behavior tolerated by them as it is understood as a public space and shared space (before pandemic Covid-10)

Fig. 2: Buying and selling activities at Pasar Baru Pulau Punjung and at Pasar Pagi Salatiga by implementing health protocols by maintaining physical distance between market traders

c) Public Space: Urban Contemporer

In contemporary urban life, public spaces act as the pulse of city life by seeking to achieve high activity vitality through organizing various events to attract city residents to gather in crowds, such as music concerts, cultural exhibitions, to running competitions wrapped in entertainment, which makes distance regulation possible to assert personal space by each user space is almost untenable.

Fig. 3: Demonstration in the Square of Tel Aviv during the covid-19 pandemic by implementing physical distancing protocols between demonstrators

The figure 3 above has shown how the Public Space/Urban Contemporer VS New-Normal (Zero) and it is diagramatise as seen below in figure 3 below.

Fig. 4: The rules of Health Protocol is one - physical distancing - has changed the conceptual understanding of public space (Indriyati, S.A., 2022)

In the situation of New Normal Era, the Public Space functions have changed. It means that the function is changed and the space identity has no longer attached to the space: The space have no meaningful as before as summarized in figure 5 below.

Public Space – Change the Function in New Normal Era

Fig. 5: The New Normal Life impacts the conceptual understanding of public space of which it changes the Conceptual space of identity (Indriyati, S.A., 2022)

Other than that, the New Normal life adopting the physical distancing requirement has an impact to change for the programmatic of the space (as shown in figure 6 below). The new normal life demands that the health aspect is the main factor influencing the architectural form and layout. From today era, a space is no longer designed based on economic value only related to space capacity, but health standard becomes priority although emotional satisfaction for users related to the identity and symbols in space will found less perceived.

SPATIAL CONCEPT – Programmatic/Pragmatic Change for Public Space (Medium Scale)

Fig. 6: The New Normal life impacts the programmatic of the space and requiring the normal standards used like Neufert Architect Data and Time Saver standards are not precisely able to be used for the guidelines of planning and designing the space (Indriyati, S.A., 2022)

d) Outdoor Café: Reduce Risks – Indoor to Outdoor Acts

Health Protocol’s orientation has also optimized the use of outdoor space to stop the spread of Covid19 virus. On of other public space like restaurants as shown in figure 7 below are now redesigning the use of their side outdoor space, allowing the guest to sit and dine in with healthier atmosphere where the Covid19 virus is not congested in the room like indoor ones.

Fig. 7: Restaurant’s redesigning their side outdoor space to avoid the Covid19 virus is not congested in the room like indoor ones (Source: Google)

Fig. 8: Dining in tents during the pandemic (Source: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/magazines/panache/dining-in-tents-during-the-pandemic-it-may-not-be-a-safe-way-to-eat-out/articleshow/79405131.cms>)

e) Workhome Stations

Other creative industry in architecture was found new in this New Normal Era is the creativity of designing work home stations as seen in figure 9 below. While pandemic is now occurred and Work from Home is all common, therefore the architect creates the special semi-outdoor workspace in the garden. It gives a sense of a normal office working psychologically, while in meeting health protocol to put health as number one priority.

Fig. 9: The creativity of designing Estudio Enterrado: Concept for a small underground working space in incorporated with all the essential elements for a small studio, by Brazilian Architect the working space becomes a discrete and private solution for a home (Source: <https://estamuycool.com/bunker-estudio-enterrado-por-igor-leal/>)

f) New Normal Era: Indoor Space

Having said the public and outdoor ones, the indoor space in the New Normal Era is to be explored. The demand for a healthy of any space to minimize the risk of being infected with Covid19 is required. In architectural design activities during the new normal, adjustments to spatial programming will change the design guidelines and rules, which has been emphasizing on efficiency when referring to modern architecture and has been emphasizing on emotional needs when referring to postmodern architecture. The new normal life demands that the health aspect is the main factor influencing the architectural form and layout. A space is no longer designed based on economic value related to space capacity, effectiveness of carrying out activities in space, and ease of mobilization between spaces, as well as space design that is able to provide emotional satisfaction for users related to the identity and symbols in space and the most important is to adopt the Health Protocols regulations.

g) Indoor Treatments: Restaurants-Workspace-Classroom

Indoor space in the New Normal Era, like Restaurant, Workspace and Classroom are those affected in terms of the application of the Health Protocols. Physical distancing is adopted which therefore impacts on the room design as shown in the figures number 10 to 14 below.

Fig. 10: Workstation layout to change

(Source: Neufert Architect Data)

Fig.11: Workplace next: post-pandemic design

(Source:<https://leoadaly.com/perspectives/workplace-next-post-pandemic-design-for-companies-and-developers/>)

h) Architecture Classroom: UCLA University

Fig. 12: Physical distancing impact the new seats arrangement and capacity of room

(Source:<https://www.google.com/search?q=UCLA+Classroom+pandemic+covid>)

i) Restaurants

Fig. 13: Adjusting the furniture in the restaurant area during the Covid-19 pandemic and designing furniture for the new normal life.

During the pandemic, spatial efforts that are considered emergency have been widely practiced by restricting and spacing visitors in public spaces by arranging spatial layouts and furniture layouts that prevent mass crowds from occurring.

Adjustment of furniture design that allows users to maintain a safe distance according to health protocols, such as single seater chairs that are only intended for 1 person at a safe distance from other seat holders or from circulation paths designated for space users to pass.

Fig. 14: Furniture design adjustments that allow users to maintain a safe distance according to health protocols, such as single seater chairs that are only intended for 1 person with a safe distance from other chair holders

Having said that all thought and examples, the Spatial Concept has proposed concerning the programmatic and pragmatic changes for Indoor (room). It can be seen in figure 15 below. It shows what to change and end up with modifying the architect’s standard of room that commonly used. The room standards for building design are required to be formulated. The normal standards used like Neufert Architect Data and Time Saver standards are not precisely able to be used for the guidelines of designing the buildings.

SPATIAL CONCEPT – Programmatic/Pragmatic Change for Indoor Space (Room)

Fig. 15: Diagram of Spatial Concept (Indriyati, S.A., 2022)

B. Technology Conceptual

Architectural technology used is responsible to help stopping the spread of the Covid-19 Virus in this New-Normal era. The figure 16 below describes how Architectural Technology requirements for Building design in New-Normal Era.

Fig. 16: Architectural Technology requirements for Building design in New-Normal Era (Indriyati, S.A., 2022)

Architectural Technology aspects are required to stop the spread of the Covid-19 virus in space. There are three criterias to see once the construction will proceed. The building materials must support the building sustainability to use. The criteria described as follows:

- New building material has high durability against routine disinfectant spraying;
- Material technology with the characteristics of not allowing the Covid-19 virus stays in the long term, even possible to kill the Covid-19 virus attached to the material;
- The material specifications were chosen avoiding the potential for the spreading over of the Covid-19 virus

through architectural elements that are frequently hold and use communally can be suppressed, such as railings, frames, door openings, furniture, etc.

a) Urban Contemporer Issues: Air Conditioning

The frequent use of air conditioning in the urban areas is one issue. The rapid spread of the Covid-19 virus in the contemporary urban environment is thought to be due to joint activities in closed spaces and public transportation using air conditioning. The risk of spreading the Covid-19 virus will increase in an indoor room with minimal openings and a high level of space congestion, especially if you continuously rely on air conditioning for air circulation in the room. Experts in the physical field of buildings together with experts in the health sector should look for solutions to the effect of natural lighting and ventilation systems on the spread of the Covid-19 virus in the room related to the humidity level of the room, wind flowing in and out of the room, the level of sunlight in the room, etc so that appropriate lighting and ventilation technology can be decided to stop the spread of the virus in the room. Architectural technology adjustment in the context of a new normal life requires a paradigm shift.

Fig. 17: Adjustment of architectural technology aspects in the context of a new normal life requires a paradigm shift in the creation of technology which is no longer limited to being influenced by economic value, body comfort, user safety, and aesthetics, but also must meet room health standards according to health protocols that have been set to break the spread Covid-19 virus indoors

(Source: Google

[https://www.google.com/search?q=aircon+restaurant+pandemic&tbm=isch&ved=\)](https://www.google.com/search?q=aircon+restaurant+pandemic&tbm=isch&ved=)

b) Users' Hygiene

Stopping the spread of the Covid-19 virus, especially in public spaces, is also closely related to hygiene technology, so that room users can clean their body parts regularly, such as by providing public washbasins equipped with soap or spraying spots of disinfectant for luggage and hand sanitizers that are distributed within a certain radius with an aesthetic and easily recognizable design. The living environment should appear with good visual quality according to architectural rules while at the same time complying with health protocols related to the

level of cleanliness of the room and the users of the space during activities in the room. Touchless material selection is also a consideration (sensory).

Fig. 18: The use of hygiene technologies to control cleanliness of the room and the users' health – Automatic doors and touchless lift buttons (Source: Google)

V. CONCLUSION

Having discussed how is pandemic's impacts on architecture as seen in the figure 19, as follows:

Fig. 19: Diagram of Pandemic's impacts on Architecture (Indriyati, S.A., 2022)

Novelty of the research has found out the Pragmatic changes of public space, outdoor space, semi-outdoor rooms, combined functions rooms for home, workplace design, special interior design as well as architectural technology which those all the impacts of the Pandemic's New-Normal Era. Changes and adjustments to spatial concepts and technological concepts in architecture will change the architectural design paradigm by prioritizing the Hygiene space and users' health.

The Concept of Application of New Normal Design - Indoor and Outdoor Buildings can be proposed, as follows:

- Functional Design, where this functional design becomes a good innovation
- Greenery Building Design, where plants and vegetation for inside or outside the building. It is useful for the room to always get oxygen (clean air) which is very important for the health of users and can provide comfort and a relaxed and calm atmosphere for users.
- Natural Lighting by using skylights and windows as access to incoming sunlight to have the brighter room and reduces electricity consumption in the evening. This natural lighting is also used for lighting in outdoor buildings such as parks.

- Good Air Circulation, by making cross ventilation, building walls at least 3 meters high, and creating green open spaces around the building.
- Smart Building by using sensors for the door locks, elevators, sensors, sink sensors, door sensors, attendance, etc.
- The application of protocols carried out in the building is also very necessary due to many contacts between users, by applying the provision of hand washing/hand sanitizer, a place to check the temperature, and most importantly the existence of physical distancing between humans in a building or location. Physical distancing here applied in all parts of the site both inside and outside buildings such as parks.
- Implementing a cubicle design to make users feel safe from physical contact with other users with a distance of 1.5 – 2 meters between a row of cubicle tables that are used as user circulation in the room.
- Provision of a green open space for outdoor activities and can be refreshing for users or visitors and has an effect on health as well.
- Provide lots of park benches and plan their placement to reduce the density of park chairs to avoid physical contact between users or visitors and also as a place for visitors to rest or enjoy the natural air.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Akbar, Rus. Okezone. (2020). *Tradisional Dharmasraya Sumbar*, Rus Akbar. <https://news.okezone.com/read/2020/05/03/340/2208606/melihat-physical-distancing-di-pasar-tradisional-dharmasraya-sumbar>, Melihat *Physical Distancing* di Pasar
- [2.] Berkaf & BPS. (2016). Creative Economy GDP Contribution Based on 16 Sub-sectors in 2016: Results of the Special Creative Economy Survey.
- [3.] Burhan, Erlina et all. (2020). *Buku Pedoman Tatalaksana COVID19*. <https://www.papdi.or.id/pdfs/983/Buku%20Pedoman%20Tatalaksana%20COVID-19%205OP%20Edisi%203%202020.pdf>
- [4.] Burhan, Endi. (2012). *Time Saver Standart of Building Type*, 2nd Edition, LP3A, 2012.
- [5.] Economic Times. (2021). *Dining in tents during the pandemic? It may not be a safe way to eat out*. <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/magazines/panache/dining-in-tents-during-the-pandemic-it-may-not-be-a-safe-way-to-eat-out/articleshow/79405131.cms>
- [6.] Kluge, Hans, Henri, P. Kluge. (2021). *The facilities must apply strictly the regulation in the implementation of the new normal life* (The Decree of the Minister of Health of Republic Indonesia Number HK.01.07/MENKES/328/2020). <https://www.euro.who.int/en/about-us/regional-director>
- [7.] Harikesa, I., Wayan. (2020). *Industri Revolution 40 Strengthening: The Creative Economy Sectors through Bekraf Implementation Programs*. Faculty of Social and Political Science, International Relations Major Jenderal Achmad Yani University (UNJANI). https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342702268_INDUSTRI_REVOLUTION_40_STRENGTHENING_THE_CREATIVE_ECONOMY_SECTORS_THROUGH_BEKRAF_IMPLEMENTATION_PROGRAMS
- [8.] Igorleigor. (2020). Estudio Enterrado: Concept for a small underground working space in corporated with all the essential elements for a small studio. The working space becomes a discrete and private solution for a home office. <https://estamuycool.com/bunker-estudio-enterrado-por-igor-leal/>
- [9.] Google.com
- [10.] GoWork.com
- [11.] Howkins, John. (2015). *Interview Donna Ghelfi of the world intellectual Property Organisation (WHO)*. https://id.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ekonomi_kreatif - Ekonomi Kreatif
- [12.] Liebermann & Schwartz, CNN. (2020). *Thousands of Israelis Protest Against Netanyahu, Two Meters Apart*. <https://edition.cnn.com/2020/04/20/middleeast/israel-protest-social-distancing-intl/index.html>
- [13.] Neufert, Architect Data Physical distancing impact the new seats arrangement and capacity of room. (2022). <https://www.google.com/search?q=UCLA+Classroom+pandemic+covid>
- [14.] Sugihamreta, I Dewa Gde. (2022). *Respon Kebijakan: Mitigasi Dampak Wabah Covid19 pada Sektor Pariwisata*. <https://doi.org/10.36574/jpp.v4i2.113>, <https://journal.bappenas.go.id/index.php/jpp/article/view/113>
- [15.] The Decree of the Minister of Health Number HK.01.07/MENKES/328/2020. (2020). Guidelines for the Prevention and Control of Covid-19 in Office and Industrial Workplaces in Supporting Business Continuity in a Pandemic Situation.
- [16.] The Indonesian Creative Economy Agency (Berkaf). (2019). *Establishment of The Creative Economy Agency (Badan Ekonomi Kreatif – Bekraf)*. <https://en.unesco.org/creativity/policy-monitoring-platform/establishment-creative-economy>
- [17.] The Indonesian Standard Classification of Business Fields (KBLI) Robbins, Heater. (2022). *Workplace Next: Post-Pandemic Design for Companies and Developers*. <https://leoadaly.com/perspectives/workplace-next-post-pandemic-design-for-companies-and-developers/>